

ISSUES OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' LITERACY THROUGH VARIOUS PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the issues of effective use of various pedagogical technologies in improving students' literary literacy. Today, the formation of literary knowledge and skills on the basis of innovative approaches, modern information and communication technologies, interactive methods and creative educational methods in the educational process is gaining urgent importance. The study highlights the role and importance of modern pedagogical approaches in teaching literature, and analyzes the technologies that serve to develop students' creative thinking. Also, the article shows the advantages of content enrichment of literature classes, didactic games, group work, problem-based teaching and the use of electronic tools. The authors also studied the possibilities of using modern educational platforms and multimedia materials to improve students' literary literacy.

INTRODUCTION

The foundation of literary education consists of the concepts of the purpose, tasks, and content of teaching literature. Before engaging in any pedagogical activity, it is necessary to answer the questions of who, why, and what. The primary task is to prepare a reader from an ordinary student, to form a student who can be influenced by artistic words, feel their charm, recognize true literary works, analyze the works read, draw conclusions from them, express their views fluently both orally and in writing, and turn reading literary works into a primary life necessity [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is known that the content of education is reflected in concepts, curricula, standards, textbooks, and manuals. In education, the life experience of the learner and their ability to absorb information largely depend on their age characteristics. Literature as a subject is not taught in primary school. However, the subject of "Reading Book," which serves as the initial component of literary education, is taught. In primary school reading lessons, literary-aesthetic education is not set as the main goal. Therefore, literary materials are not provided systematically. The book includes texts related to literature as well as those concerning history, geography, and ethics.

At this stage, the main objectives are:

- a) Reading accurately, fluently, and expressively,
- b) Understanding what is read and being able to explain it,
- c) Developing oral speech based on the learned material,
- d) Developing writing skills and literacy [2].

Aesthetic or comprehensive didactic analysis of the studied materials is not considered a task in primary school; instead, drawing didactic conclusions from the read materials is deemed essential. Depending on the level and preparation of students, extensive didactic analysis of texts can be introduced in grades 3-4, and elements of aesthetic analysis can also be incorporated.

In these grades, identifying the rhyme of poems, paying attention to the importance of rhyme in ensuring the musicality of poetry, and focusing on wordplay can be considered elements of aesthetic analysis. In secondary grades, the skills developed in primary grades are enhanced and elevated to the level of proficiency.

At this stage, didactic analysis of the studied works is the primary task, while aesthetic analysis is not given primary importance (i.e., it is not considered a primary task) [3]. However, aesthetic analysis is not neglected. It should be noted that according to the curriculum, folklore samples such as proverbs, riddles, and fairy tales are introduced in the 5th grade.

This is logical according to the age characteristics of students since it is easier and more convenient to teach them based on these literary materials and it corresponds to the intended goals and objectives. Unlike in primary school, texts are subjected to complete didactic analysis.

Drawing lessons from good deeds and noble heroes, identifying the basis and factors of the goodness of good characters and the badness of bad characters, analyzing the characteristic aspects, behavior, and speech of the characters lead the study of works. The selected literary material is significantly complicated. At this age, the child develops physically, physiologically, and mentally day by day, week by week, and month by month.

Therefore, the teacher's task is to ensure the student's intellectual and spiritual development based on the selected teaching material corresponding to this growth. In this process, the need to improve the requirements and form of work analysis comes to the forefront.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

At the current stage of the development of science and social progress, it has become evident to everyone that it is impossible to implement these tasks using the traditional methods in the education system that have already outlived their time. As in other areas of continuous education, it has been proven by life itself that no progress can be achieved in the process of literary education without technological advancement [4].

In scientific and encyclopedic literature, the concept of "technology" is viewed from different perspectives, such as a set of methods aimed at achieving a specific goal, methods used in activities, and rules for organizing activities. For instance, the "Encyclopedic Dictionary" defines it as "a science aimed at improving the methods of preparing and

processing raw materials, materials, and semi-finished products in various sectors of the national economy."

Looking at the history of the issue, it can be concluded that scientific and technological advancements resulting from the production of goods and the emergence of new approaches to their creation have contributed to the emergence of the concept of technology. It is enough to recall the widespread use of the term "Andijan Technology" related to cotton seed planting in the 1970s. It is no secret that there is a significant difference between the products manufactured in the current era of scientific and technological progress and those produced earlier.

Social progress cannot be imagined without scientific development and the activities of highly educated specialists. Therefore, it is a very urgent task for the higher education system to ensure that students quickly absorb the modern flow of information, develop their research skills, and improve their individual and independent working skills. The reason for this is that as production conditions change, the quality, knowledge, skills, and competencies of specialists trained under traditional education cannot meet the requirements placed upon them. Accordingly, preparing specialists who meet the ever-growing demands of accelerated scientific and technological progress requires enhancing teaching methods and effectively using visual teaching methods.

In recent years, much work has been done to accelerate teaching through the integration of educational sciences. For example, in the field of humanitarian education, combining subjects like the native language, children's literature, and folklore into a single course raises the question: To what extent is this approach justified? The issue becomes more evident when considering the possibility of one teacher teaching all these subjects, which illustrates how contradictory the problem can be.

In fact, efforts have previously been made to integrate such educational subjects. For instance, in 1919, a program created for seven-year schools consolidated all subjects into four courses: social sciences, natural sciences, and exact sciences. The idea of technologizing the education system related to social progress was first proposed in the United States and Western European countries, and over time, various approaches were applied to it. In developed countries, particular attention is paid to humanizing education through educational technologies aimed at socializing individuals [5].

Although the terms method, methodology, technology, and pedagogical technology are often used interchangeably, they do not fully encompass the meaning of educational technology. An educational method refers to the method of solving tasks in the learning process through the collaboration of the teacher and the student. Educational methodology represents a set of scientifically and methodologically based methods, techniques, and styles for teaching a specific subject.

Educational technology, on the other hand, refers to the process of developing and managing a system of methods, techniques, and tools designed to achieve a specific, predetermined educational goal within a comprehensive system through a step-by-step process that guarantees the desired outcome.

Educational technology refers to the doctrine of information related to organizing the educational process with high skill at the level of art. It possesses characteristics of

scientificity, practicality, descriptiveness, and systematicity as a pedagogical system applied to practice. Pedagogical technology is a scientifically grounded system designed and organized based on a project planned for a certain period, aimed at achieving a specific goal, and ensuring the attainment of that goal.

As with any academic subject in the education system, social progress plays an important role in the development of literature teaching methodology. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, "On Additional Measures to Improve the System of Monitoring Education Quality" (Decree No. PQ-4119), and the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Enhancing Reading Culture and Reading Skills Among Young People, Increasing the Intellectual Potential and Literary-Aesthetic Level of Our Children" necessitate serious reflection on the current state of literature teaching methodology.

Society is changing, and attitudes toward life are evolving. The deep-rooted integration of the Internet and the continuous growth of the flow of information require a new approach to education and training through the technologization of the educational system.

Pedagogical education aims to achieve educational goals through the development of the learner's personality, which relies on the level of knowledge and skills acquired during this process, as well as the interest and activity of the students. It is evident that the activity of the learner in this process is the main substance of their development as a person.

In technologizing the process of literary education, it is aimed to achieve high results in a short period without excessive mental and physical effort, and without wasting unnecessary time, ensuring that students acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies at an adequate level.

Modern pedagogical approaches: the integration of learner-centered, competency-based, and acmeological education, finding their intersection points, and applying them in a blended form in the educational process contribute to improving the quality of education, particularly the effectiveness of literary education. The correctness of this scientific hypothesis can be justified by the following factors [6]:

1. The application of leading paradigms in the pedagogical field, such as cognitive, personal, cultural, and competence paradigms, requires the integration of modern pedagogical approaches in the teaching process of a specific subject or lesson.

2. It is necessary to consider all of these paradigms when determining the prospects for the development of literary education and making strategic decisions, as they appear as parts of a whole system.

3. Placing the learner at the center of the educational process, creating all the necessary conditions for their learning (learner-centered approach), identifying and developing their talents (acmeological approach), and forming literary education competencies (competency-based approach) are not denied by any of these approaches; on the contrary, they support each other.

4. Modern pedagogical approaches do not contradict each other; instead, they complement one another.

5. Interactive methods are a common feature of modern pedagogical approaches and serve to ensure their interconnection, consistency, and relevance.

The level of preparedness of a literature teacher in performing professional tasks is a key factor in their pedagogical activity. The teacher's professional skill refers to their theoretical and practical readiness for pedagogical activity. Professional skill is related to the knowledge and skills associated with the main aspects of a literature teacher's activity, and it is appropriate to understand it as an essential condition for the effectiveness of professional-pedagogical activity.

In turn, the teacher's professional skill and competence are not only dependent on acquiring various knowledge and skills, but they must also encompass important personal qualities and experience. According to the professional standards of a literature teacher's position, they must possess the necessary personal qualities and professional skills to carry out their activities effectively.

During the pedagogical experimental process, attention was paid to developing such professional competencies in literature teachers at general education schools.

In accordance with modern requirements, the preparation of contemporary literature teachers in higher education institutions plays a significant role in shaping their professionalism. For this preparation process to be effective and meet the demands of the education labor market, it is essential to establish proper, mutually beneficial cooperation between higher education institutions and general education schools.

Currently, in the example of literary education, there exists a certain level of cooperation based on the principle of harmony between theory and practice. However, it is difficult to say that this cooperation is mutually beneficial. There are issues that need to be resolved concerning cooperation. As the most appropriate innovative solution to eliminate these problems, we propose the concept of a literary education cluster.

The issue of cooperation between higher education institutions and general education schools begins with setting specific goals. In this regard, the goal of higher education institutions is to admit talented applicants, while the goal of general education schools is to increase the number of graduates entering higher education institutions.

Today, the personal and professional self-determination of general education school graduates remains a problem primarily for the students themselves or their parents. This is explained by the weakness of integration between higher education and school curricula, which is evident at a rather severe level in general secondary education.

Moreover, the motivation of school students towards education remains low; there is a need for scientifically oriented extracurricular educational processes, but practical implementation is lacking. A large number of graduates from pedagogical higher education institutions often do not wish to work in their chosen field.

During the pedagogical experimental work, attention was paid to increasing the activity of literature teachers at general education schools, promoting non-standard and critical thinking, and improving lessons based on modern pedagogical approaches.

The plan also includes using the potential of professors and teachers from higher education institutions to nurture literature teachers who view lesson activities as a creative process, are not afraid of innovations, and actively apply them in their teaching practice.

The teacher is the central figure in the educational process, distinguished by their activity, unique professional competencies, non-standard and creative thinking, and their

continuous improvement of pedagogical skills through the application of educational technologies. To possess high-quality professional competence, a literature teacher is required to have professionally significant personal qualities, pedagogical abilities, continuous self-improvement, pedagogical creativity, and innovation.

Based on this, the purpose of the 'Innovative Teacher' project is as follows: to enhance the effectiveness of literature lessons by developing mechanisms for implementing modern pedagogical approaches in literature lessons, and to cultivate skills of non-standard and critical thinking, as well as viewing lessons as a creative process among teachers.

The tasks of the 'Innovative Teacher' project are as follows [8]:

Identifying the level of awareness of innovations among literature teachers in general education schools;

Determining teachers' attitudes towards new ideas and innovations;

Developing requirements for an innovative literature teacher;

Monitoring the effectiveness of the lessons conducted by teachers involved in the experimental work;

Assisting literature teachers in general education schools in improving their knowledge of modern pedagogical approaches;

Enhancing the quality and effectiveness of literature lessons based on advanced foreign experiences.

The application of advanced innovative approaches in education remains one of the most pressing issues in the system. This requires improving the innovative environment in the field, developing its forms, and enhancing the activities of innovation centers. To achieve this, technological processes within the system and objective principles must be analyzed from the perspective of progress.

Innovations in the education system are the result of integrating knowledge and acquired experiences, reflecting in the processes of science, education, and production. This implies the implementation of innovations that serve as a basis for efficiency within the system. Innovative processes depend on various factors such as organizing and managing specific types of activities, the general level and interests of specialists in the field, the mentality of the nation, the state's policy in this area, scientific and educational achievements, and the potential of the education system.

Innovative processes in literature education occur by applying advanced foreign experiences and modern pedagogical approaches to the educational process. The era of traditional approaches in literature education has ended.

RESULTS

Working with literary texts, understanding the life truths within them, and developing skills to draw conclusions are some of the main issues of modern literature education. This approach increases students' adaptability to real-life situations.

Modern literature education plays a significant role in developing students' ability to express their thoughts clearly and systematically. These requirements align with the standards of international assessment programs (PISA — Programme for International Student Assessment).

Organizing literature lessons based on modern pedagogical approaches will contribute to improving the country's position in the global ranking of education systems. After all, ensuring that the knowledge, skills, and competencies acquired in general education schools can be effectively applied in real-life situations is one of the main goals of modern education.

One of the fundamental principles of didactic analysis of a literary work is the principle of the primacy of aesthetic foundations. The analysis of a literary work should primarily focus on discovering aspects of beauty, elegance, and goodness. The principle of individuality also plays a significant role in the educational analysis of literary works.

A literary work is a product of creativity. Any creative process is always the result of the unique activity of a particular individual. Therefore, it is impossible to present or convey a literary work, which is the result of an individual's unique, personal activity, to all students in a classroom simultaneously and uniformly.

Since the goal of literary education is to shape the personality of students by conveying the creative product from the creator's heart to the young hearts, it becomes clear that this goal can only be achieved by considering that the heart cannot be universal, and that each student in the classroom has their own unique psychology, emotional experiences, sensitivity, and aesthetic experience.

The principle of emotionality also plays an essential role in effectively implementing didactic analysis. As artistic literature itself is a phenomenon based on emotions, the process of studying it must also be filled with emotions, which is both natural and necessary.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Innovations in literature education take place in the form of an activity system of educational institutions aimed at achieving specific goals, which are based on the integration of theory and practice and lead to qualitative changes. Innovations cannot occur without initiative.

Teaching depends on multiple factors and is a process based on the principle of development, which occurs through the combination of various tools and complex technologies. The possibilities for improving this process are diverse, and in every classroom of teachers and students, these possibilities reveal themselves differently.

Therefore, it becomes evident that introducing new initiatives and innovations into education is a process directly related to the teacher's personality and their professional and creative abilities.

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